

NEWSLETTER

COMPASsCO₂

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Issue : VII

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action (RIA) under grant agreement No. 958418

Team: 12 partners
from 7 countries

Research focus: New
particles, metal alloys
and heat exchanger

Duration: 1
November 2020 –
30 April 2025

Status of Implementation

The project is now entering into its final implementation stages. Many significant results, deliverables, milestones have been achieved and duly documented in order to share knowledge and advance progress in high-temperature concentrating solar technology applications. All public deliverables and main activity reports are freely accessible through the project's website: <https://www.compassco2.eu/>. The section below summarizes the main achievements by work package.

WP2 – DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF PARTICLES

Testing of the novel granulated Gen4 particles (internal/development name: FerOx) developed by Saint-Gobain has continued. In particular, thermocyclic tests have been conducted at DFI with coated Gen4 particles (see Fig. 1). The particles coated by CIEMAT, DLR and DFI do not show any optical degradation even after 3000 hours of testing. The DLR coating even improves the solar absorptance throughout testing, indicating that the heat treatment after coating deposition was not long enough to complete the curing process. The results of the thermocyclic exposure test are in good agreement with the previously conducted static exposure test at 1000°C.

In addition, abrasion testing at operational temperature has been conducted. The

measurements carried out confirm that the Gen4 particles are superior in terms of mechanical properties compared to Gen3: less particle breakage and cracking is observed (see Fig.2). Gen4 particles maintain their shape after particle-particle impacts at 5m/s and 950°C, confirming their adequacy for solar tower receiver applications. However, a slight degradation in the absorptance of the coatings can be measured. This absorptance decay can be visually confirmed with pictures (see Fig. 2c), indicating partial removal of the coating. But even after impact numbers simulating 10 operational years, the solar absorptance of the coated particles is still 4-12%-points higher (depending on the coating type) than non-coated Gen4 particles (83.3%).

a)

Figure 1: a) Cyclic thermal stability testing of particles in muffle furnace at 1000°C. b) Evolution of the solar absorptance of coated Gen4 particles.

b)

Figure 2: a) Gen4 particle after ~7640 impacts at 950°C and 5 m/s. b) partially broken Gen3 particle after ~7770 impacts c) Coated Gen3 particle showing cracks and partial coating loss after ~7770 impacts.

WP3 - DEVELOPMENT OF METALS

Exciting progress has been made in developing new high-temperature materials and coatings through COMPASSCO₂ WP3. Two significant papers were published detailing breakthroughs in these areas. The first paper introduces a novel chromium/silicon slurry coating process for high-temperature oxidation protection. Adding silicon enabled liquid phase sintering during coating application. Coatings around 150 μm thick were achieved on nickel superalloys. Oxidation testing at 900°C showed the Cr/Si coatings provide excellent protection against internal aluminium oxidation compared to uncoated alloys (Fig.3a). The second paper

reports on chromium-based body-centred cubic "superalloys" strengthened by iron additions. Computational modelling predicted and experiments validated that iron increases the volume fraction of ordered BCC precipitates, resulting in excellent high-temperature strength up to 1000°C (Fig.3b) and remarkably slow coarsening rates outperforming many existing superalloys. These advancements in new high-temperature materials and coatings are important milestones as WP3 continues developing enabling technologies for next-generation concentrated solar power applications.

Novel Cr/Si-Slurry Diffusion Coatings for High Temperatures

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Chromium-based bcc-superalloys strengthened by iron supplements

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Figure 3: Development of new high-temperature materials and coatings. a) Improvement of oxidation resistance by Cr/Si slurry coating. b) Improvement of high-temperature strength by bcc-superalloy design.

WP4 - EVALUATION AND MODELING OF METAL/MEDIUM INTERACTION

The state-of-the-art and new (WP3) materials are being fully characterized for their performance in the COMPAS_{CO₂} heat exchanger aggressive environments. Deliverable 4.2 'Wear and mechanical property evaluation' was submitted by CIEMAT in April, which focused on the state-of-the-art and newly developed materials. CIEMAT also completed the milestone 4.3 'Mechanically stable material' in the last month. Long term oxidation tests at 700°C and 900°C are ongoing at CIEMAT of the Cr-Si coated alloys. The new Cr-Si coatings

were also investigated regarding their cyclic oxidation performance at FZJ (Fig.4), in addition to the bulk new Cr alloys (from UoB). The new materials and coatings are showing improved behavior when compared to their baseline or uncoated counterparts. The majority of the exposure and creep tests have been completed, and the current WP4 focus is on in-depth characterization of the various degradation mechanisms and underlying microstructural changes. This data is being communicated to VTT for their lifetime modeling efforts.

Figure 4: Mass change over exposure time with corresponding scanning electron microscopy images of Cr-Si-coated IN617 surface cross-sections after exposure under air and CO₂. Courtesy of FZJ.

WP5 – TECHNOLOGY VALIDATION

An experimental facility for particle heating has been successfully operated at CVR, accumulating several hundred hours of operation so far. The primary objective of this activity is to investigate the abrasion and wear characteristics of selected materials intended for use in manufacturing the potential tube bundle of the particle heat exchanger. Various material samples and coatings, in form of a tubes with outer diameters of 21.3 mm and 13.7 mm (as depicted in Fig.5a) are subjected to a steady particle flow at temperatures up to 750°C

and particles velocities reaching up to 8mm/s. Additionally, several tubes are preloaded with internal pressure to induce creep conditions. Periodic scans of these tubes are conducted using a 3D laser scanner to detect any deformation (depicted in Fig.5b). This method holds potential for in-situ heat exchanger inspections and life time assessment.

The experiments are scheduled to continue until the second half of 2024 with the aim of achieving a cumulative runtime of 1000 hours.

Figure 5: a) Test section of the experimental facility. Assembled with variety of material samples and coatings. b) Pressurized samples are being periodically scanned with 3D laser scanner to detect any deformation caused by material creep

Papers produced by COMPASsCO₂ Team

Three papers were produced by the COMPASsCO₂ team during this last 6-month period.

Kerbstadt, M.; White, E.M.H.; Galetz, M.C. Novel Cr/Si-Slurry Diffusion Coatings for High Temperatures. *Materials* 2023, 16, 7480. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16237480>

Farchado, M.; San Vicente, G.; Barandica, N.; Sutter, F.; Alkan G.; Sánchez-Señorán, D.; Morales, Ángel. Performance improvement of CSP particle receivers by depositing spinel absorber coatings. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, Volume 266, 2024.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2023.112681>

Menichetti, E et al. New Materials for sCO₂ Heat Exchangers in Next Generation Concentrating Solar Plants: COMPASsCO₂ Contribution. March 2024. https://www.compassco2.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/20240319_InformativePaper2_COMPASsCO2.pdf

COMPASsCO₂ Participation at Conferences

LEAD PARTNER	EVENT VENUE DATE	TITLE OF THE PRESENTATION
UoB	BCC-SNOW Plansee, Austria 8-9/2/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oxidation behaviour of novel chromium-based bcc-superalloys Cr(Fe)-NiA - Chromium-based bcc-superalloys strengthened by iron supplements - Bcc-Superalloys: bcc refractory metals reinforced by ordered-bcc intermetallic precipitates
UoB	TMS2024 Orlando, USA 4-8/3/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High temperature behaviour of novel chromium superalloys - Nano-structured Cr-superalloys in Advanced Concentrated Solar Plant Environments - Bcc-Superalloys: Refractory Metal bcc Matrix, Reinforced by Ordered-bcc Intermetallic Precipitates
SGCREE	SG/ESPCI - Materials for ecological transition Paris, France 14/3/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General information of the COMPASsCO₂ project

Meetings

Quarterly Phone Call - The call was organized on 12 January 2024 to discuss the overall progress of the project and the preparation for the Sixth General Assembly and the Second Review Meeting. OMEC team led the discussion on dissemination and communication activities.

Second Review Meeting – The Second Review Meeting of the Horizon 2020 project

“Components’ and Materials’ Performance for Advanced Solar Supercritical CO₂ Powerplants – COMPASsCO₂” took place on 21 March 2024, online. In addition to project participants, the European Commission Project Officer and an external reviewer attended in order to assess the work conducted during the past 36 months of implementation and provide recommendations for the next phase.

COMPASsCO₂ Partners attending the online second review meeting

Sixth General Assembly Meeting - The Sixth GA Meeting took place on January 31st and February 1st, 2024 at Saint-Gobain Research Provence in Cavailon, France. The COMPASsCO₂ team discussed the overall

progress, the preparation for the Review Meeting for the second reporting period of the project, on-going activities, challenges, and next steps. A technical visit to Saint-Gobain Research Provence Laboratories was also organized.

COMPASsCO₂ Partners attending the Sixth Project Meeting at SGREE

COMPASsCO₂ at “Hannover Messe 2024”

Florian Lebendig from FZJ attended the world's leading trade fair for industry that was organized from 22 to 26 April 2024 at Hannover, Germany. Florian also met with Ms. Victoria Petrova, Head

of Unit (HaDEA, Industry Unit) and discussed about the progress made by the COMPASsCO₂ project.

Joint Dissemination Activity at MSE2024

In collaboration with other research consortia (ACHIEF, HIPERMAT, topAM), COMPASsCO₂ is co-organizing a joint session at MSE 2024 (24-26 September 2024, Hybrid (Darmstadt & online) - F02 Session: High Performance Materials for Sustainable Energy Applications).

This symposium will address recent advances in the field of novel high performance materials and components (according to aims of projects under the Horizon 2020 framework under, call LC-SPIRE-08-2020) by addressing materials

design concepts, new materials as bulk materials or as coatings (metallic and ceramic), and technologies for their development, with the final aim of manufacturing components for the industrial applications.

More details at: <https://mse-congress.de/>

How to Get Involved in COMPASsCO₂ Activities

Become a member of the project's stakeholders' network

Whether you want to learn more about specific WP activities, collaborate with the consortium or act as an external expert, kindly contact us at contact@compassco2.eu. We will keep you updated about project activities, invite you to attend the project's public events and ask your feedback on the progress and main outcomes of the project.

Check our website and follow us on social media networks

LinkedIn

<https://www.compassco2.eu/>

THANK YOU

For more information

Check the project's website: www.compassco2.eu

Contact us: contact@compassco2.eu

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